

CULTURAL PATRIARCHY: A WEAPON DEPLOYED TOWARDS FEMALE GENDER

OAIKHENA, I. Marvellous *Ph.D*

Centre for Research and Development of Esan Land (CERDEL)

Glorious Vision University, Ogwa,

Edo State Nigeria

prince_marv12@yahoo.ca

Abstract

Culture is associated with belief system, values customs artifacts and behaviour that is associated with the people in a society, community or environment. It has to do with language, social habits, arts, rituals and norms that guide the interactions and lives of the people. Women are deeply involved in cultural practices across societies. They play a crucial role in the preservation of cultural norms, as they often act as custodians of traditions, ceremonies and rituals. Cultural patriarchy therefore is a pervasive framework that gives the male gender privileges to restrict the roles of women, freedom and shaping social relations and cultural expectations in our society. This study is thus set to find out how the female gender are discriminated against in our cultural environment, and why cultural patriarchy prevailed in our social system in Africa. The study adopted secondary research data generational approach. It adopted feminist theory to criticize cultural patriarchy, which explains inequality and injustice meted out to the women. The study also adopted the Maputo Protocol of 2004 which has been rectified by over 40 African countries, and an African Charter on Human and People's Right of women in Africa. The study recommended that women's rights should be respected, they should be fairly treated, allowed to hold leadership positions and given a pride of place in the society.

Keywords: Cultural patriarchy, gender, social relations, tradition.

Introduction

Cultural patriarchy has been described as a means of male dominance in both family and society. Some societies have justified gender inequalities through cultural patriarchy. The believe that the male authority and control has brought about dominance and social inequalities, necessitating social order and economic productivity. According to Godelier (1981) he posits that "it is crucial to pinpoint the real importance, or specific weight, of

each social inequality within the hierarchy of causes that shape the functioning and evolution of our society”. Patriarchy ideology rationalizes exclusion of the female gender from participating actively in political, economic and social roles as men are leaders and providers, and women are relegated to domestic roles and subordinated. Enweonwu, et al (2023) inclined that “culture as a concept is only meaningful in the context of human society. In other words, it presumes existence of human society and is imbued with tools and skills with which the human society is enabled to work”. The cultural defense of patriarchy supports systemic gender-based violence and discrimination. Male superiority in the area of culture portrays inequalities as male dominance has legitimized patriarchy. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2022), rightly observed that “when an individual is treated equally and given opportunity to express himself, he is able to effectively utilize the talents and resources to improve the living standard of himself and those around”.

In furtherance, religion has also played significant role in cultural patriarchy, as doctrine, institutional structures and practices have given the male gender legitimacy. Religions scriptures and teachings has often defined gender roles as male dominance, while the women are restricted as caregivers. According to Karami (2021) he said that “when human has formed a society culture has also been formed”. The sustainability of cultural patriarchy perpetuates gender inequalities, limiting women from participating in activities or limiting their access to authoritative positions, as they are portrayed as subordinates, passive, and primarily valued for their appearance and nurturing roles. This hegemonic representation supports traditional gender roles, as men are associated with strength, leadership and assertiveness. Female character tends to be sexualized through their physical attractiveness or dependence on men.

In view of these, the study investigates if cultural patriarchy is a weapon deployed towards female gender; and the reasons why women are targets of cultural patriarchy in the society, as women played significant roles in providing for the family and promoting traditional beliefs across society.

Traditional values

Traditional values are long standing beliefs, customs and principles passed down from generation to generation, within a society or cultural environment. These values emphasize what is considered important or admissible in a community. It is from these values that families promote social cohesion, respect for elders, authority to stability and order in the community. These limitations are often upheld by literal interpretations of text associated or pronounced by traditional belief that associate leadership with muscularity. This was why Oaikhena observed that “in a society where there is freedom of belief, freedom of religion, the freedom to hold any opinion and belong to any association of one’s choice, these has to be tolerance”. Meanwhile Udofia (2021) quoting Chukwuemeka Eze, traditional African society has a great assert in its practice of a mode of life called communalism. This used to be the bedrock and the result of the wonderful relationship prevalent in the community as well as the purpose existence of the community and the Africa man.

In Nigeria, cultural patriarchy has seen significant growth in most communities and village settings accompanied by rigid gender roles. While the female gender constitutes the majority in terms of geographical spread, they are largely excluded from leadership roles, and positions. These disparity raises sociological questions about power, culture, and institutional control within cultural spaces. Understanding the roots of gender discrimination or cultural patriarchy within the society requires a sociological lens that considers cultural and traditional experience of women.

This could be the reason why Johnson-Bashua (2020) observed that “African culture has set mold of beliefs and values for women which are not taken lightly neither are they negotiable. Gender relations in Africa has a bearing on familial lines which assigns roles to both sex makes the household duties a woman’s principal responsibility”.

These exclusionary farmwork perpetuates patriarchal structures that limit the agency of women within communities. This leads to diminished self-esteem, restricted social influence, and limited opportunities for personal growth towards leadership roles. Discriminatory practices in communities or within societies often mirror and reinforce

broader societal inequalities. Oaikhena rightly observed that “in a society of community filled with hatred, people begin to feel suffocated and depressed, as discrimination makes miserable lives for not just those discriminated against, but everyone in the society.

Living in a patriarchy society

Despite global and national efforts to promote gender equality, female gender discrimination remains a persistent issue within many cultural communities. In most communities in Africa there is the growing concern over the limited roles and recognition accorded to women in community leadership and decision making. This was why Salisu et al (2024) observed that “literatures has shown that controversy over the proper role of public administration in the political process is just too far from being resolved”. For instance, the Esan women in Edo State, Nigeria, experience cultural patriarchy. Under the Esan customary laws women face significant discrimination, especially in matter of inheritance, succession and burial rites, where the rule of primogenitures often excludes daughters and widows from inheriting properties. According to Enakireru and Edewor (2024), quoting Magbele (2016), they asserted that “customary laws among various tribes in Nigeria typically prohibit women from inheriting the estates of their deceased husbands and fathers. Nonetheless, certain customary laws grant women a limited right to inherit such estates”. Inheritance can be divided into two primary categories: testamentary and intestate. In cases of testamentary inheritance, the deceased has documented their wishes through a formal will, whereas in intestate inheritance, the deceased has passed away without leaving such a document. Property held by an individual can be categorized as either "personal" or "real" property (African Customary and Religious Law Review 1 (2020).

Moreso, during Esan burial ceremonies, gender discrimination is prevalent. Women are excluded from participating in key funeral rites, which is also associated with inheritance. The Esan culture only recognized the male – especially the first-born male child, while daughters and widows are generally barred from certain significant roles. This clearly indicate the notion that men hold authority and social values, while the women are relegated and marginalized in both family and community life. These

reinforces the idea that women are less capable of leadership responsibilities and this also limit them from family resources and social recognition. Additionally, Esan women actively participate in traditional and cultural activities, their access to authoritative positions and policy making roles appears disproportionately restricted. This reality raises critical sociological questions about the institutional structures, cultural norms, and women's right and opportunity that continues to sustain gender inequalities within Africa. According to Mofoluwawo (2014), "discrimination against women is a global phenomenon it is as old as human history".

The prescience of such discrimination undermines the principle of equity, inclusion and community development, potentially discouraging women's full participation and impacting the identity and voice. While accounts are evidence suggesting pattern of marginalization of women in Africa, there is a lack of systematic sociological investigation into the livid experience of women, the power dynamics at play, and the broader implications for social change and cultural practices.

Interrogating the sociological dynamics

Weaponizing patriarchy reinforces male dominance across social structures through legitimate ideological rationalization of gender inequality by attributing it to natural or divine order, justifying men's control over women in family business, politics and society at large. According to Makama (2013) quoting Salaam,2003, "patriarchy justifies the marginalization of women in education, economy, labour market, politics, business, family, domestic matters and inheritance".

Patriarchy imposes power relations hierarchically, as male control the female reproductive system sexually, thus reinforcing male dominance in both private and public sphere of the female gender. Men are also socialized into leadership and dominant roles, while the female folks are relegated to subordinate roles perpetuating unequal power dynamics across social institutions. These social institutions pave the way for maintaining a broader system of oppression, when marginalized women face compounded subjugation, like in the case of Esan women in Edo State as pointed earlier by the study. Compounded subjugation affects women by intensifying their oppression to several

social, economic, cultural, political and psychological consequences. As a result, there is increase in vulnerability, as they are prone to domestic violence sanctioned by societal norms. According to Oaikhena and Osawe (2012), quoting Walter 1972, they observed that “in any given economy, the various components should reflect the well-being of others. As depression in one sector invariably transfer itself to others to some extent”.

In these respect, cultural norms or processes like marriage, burial, etc, often function as mechanism of control, subjecting women to emotional physical and psychological abuse and limitations. Despite being the majority, most times in the community, women are often excluded from meaningful leadership roles. This exclusion not reflects institutional sexism, but also denies women access to authority and voice in the community. The structural discrimination undermines the moral doctrinal direction of their community as they are systematically undervalued, which could lead to emotional psychological distress. Over time, these effects can manifest to depression, self-doubt, and withdrawal from cute participation in social activities. These concerns made Oaikhena et al (2013) to observe that “people become attached to ideas over time through a social-political processes of putting their ideas into good use”.

In view of these, the sociological dynamics began to play a significant role by focusing on how the female gender face oppression embedded and reproduced across social structure, shaping women’s experiences and limiting their opportunities. Women face systematic disadvantages in several important social functions such social cohesion, moral guidance, and community formation. However, when these happens, it disrupts social balance and perpetuate systemic inequality. These symbolic practices construct and reinforces the idea that women are to be submissive and men authoritative. This authority pave way for moral dominance and gender inequality, as men hold primary power and women are largely excluded from full participation in various aspect of life. This has hindered women’s advocacy, leadership, and economic progress.

Empirical evidence has showed that gender discrimination emanates within the society or community that creates multifaceted harm. It marginalizes female voice, undermines mental well-being, and reduces long-term commitment to social institutions. At the same time, gender discrimination in Africa cannot be fully understood without

engaging with the social-cultural, historical, and post-colonial dynamics that shapes the livid realities of African women. It was in support of this assertion that Anna-Sophia (2022) on her seminar paper wrote that “in a patriarchally dominated society, gender positions construct the female role as weak, dark, emotional, domestic, inferior, and passive while the male role is depicted as strong, enlightened, rational, superior, and active”. While Western feminisms often emphasize liberal individualism and gender equality through legal and institutional reforms, Africa feminist theory offer frameworks that are deeply rooted in community, spiritual heritage, motherhood, and resistance to colonial legacies.

Fig: 1 Diagram: The Maputo Protocol of 2024

Source: Author's design 2025 using the literature

The Maputo Protocol, formally known as the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights on the Rights of Women in African is a comprehensive treaty adopted by the African Union in 2003 to promote and protect women’s right across the continent (Wikipedia). The Protocol is widely regarded as one of the most progressive human rights instruments for women globally, addressing both private and public spheres of life.

Thus, the above diagram is a clear indication of the result which could emanate if patriarchy continue to play leading roles in our community. Patriarchy against women manifest as systemic discrimination, oppression, exploitation, and violence, rooted in the historical and cultural enforcement of male dominance across all aspect of society, especially Africa. It establishes a social structure where men hold primary power and authority at the expense of women’s agency and well-being.

However, patriarchy puts pressure on men to operate in realms that they may not be gifted for. Thus, men are pressured into leadership roles they are not called to, gifted for, and equipped to fulfil while women who are called, gifted, and equipped are passed over. Women are envisioned as “temptresses,” and anything beyond superficial contract is rigorously avoided. Within appropriate boundaries, friendship between men and women (both married or single) can be spiritual and encouraged discipleship. Pursuing gender equality and justice in the society at large will not just benefit women, it will benefit men as well.

Gender-based inequality policies and social welfare programmes

Policies that are restrictive falls under the gender-based inequality and social welfare programmes. These policies limit the rights, resources, and opportunities of women. Restrictive policies, such as those that limit the rights of the female gender, perpetuates inequality by reinforcing social norms and power structures that prevent one gender from another. This could be why Oaikhena (2023) wrote that “it is the duty of society to prevent the strong, greedy, and unscrupulous individuals from exploiting the weak and over-enriching themselves at their expense”

The female gender integrates spiritual material, and communal values, which are deeply embedded in Africa societies, offering a culturally sensitive framework for social welfare and change. Women provides a valuable epistemological tool for gender studies, postcolonial theory, and cultural studies. Disparities that exist in various aspects of life limits women access to opportunities and resources. Inequalities affecting feminism in Africa pave way for economic growth that undermine human rights and sustainable development and progress necessitating ongoing efforts towards policy programmes. These programmes typically focus on economic empowerment, education, legal reforms, access to healthcare and political participation. Initiatives such as these promotes gender participation and the dismantling of systematic barriers. Systematic barriers significantly impact the welfare of women through the creation of inequalities across economic, social, cultural and political spheres. These barriers are often embedded in institution, policies, societal norms and practices. They distort opportunities for women and hinders them from decision making power and restrict their ability to support themselves and their families. Social injustice prevents transformation and economic development (Oaikhena, 2024).

As a result, deep-rooted stereotypes and cultural expectations confine women to traditional roles centered on domesticity and ecological justice. The fact that women are often underrepresented in political and leadership positions, limits their influence on policies and decision-making process affecting their welfare. The principle of fairness and fair representation in the distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, ensure that no person suffer from environmental harm or excluded from environmental benefits. Restrictive policies according to the study paved way for women to be unfortunately treated and perceived as marginalized groups in the environment or communities, as their voices are not amplified in decision – making processes and environmental programs or policies.

The welfare of women in social programs promote the economic, social and health needs through various interventions. Such interventions usually empower women, improve healthcare, enhance financial independence, and also provide social protection. Through these means, positive impact such as increased incomes, assets ownership and

reduced dependency on begging or exploitation. As a result, welfare programs for women emphasize a strong evaluation of framework to adopt and improve interventions continually, to ensuring that women benefit substantially.

Feminism theory as framework for analysis

This theory does not merely critique gender oppression, but also seek to reframe womanhood in African terms, thereby resisting both indigenous patriarchy and imported colonial ideologies. The relevance lies in its' ability to offer culturally grounded solutions to gender-based inequality, tailored to the African socio-political landscape. The early propounders of the feminist theory was Mary Wollstonecraft, whose influential work "A vindication of the Right of Women" was published in 1792, advocating for women's education and equality (Wikipedia). The feminist theory critiques patriarchal systems that uphold male dominance and challenge the exclusion of women from leadership and decision-making with the society. According to Benda (2008) wrote that "instruments to tackle specific elements of discrimination include the 1967 Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women which predated to the women's convention otherwise known as Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)".

The adoption of the feminist theory by the study is borne out of the fact that it analyses gender-based discrimination in the society. This theory aims to understand gender inequality as it encompasses ideas from diverse disciplines, exploring how social structures, power dynamics and cultural norms contributes to women's oppression and inequality. The evolvment of this theory largely emerges from the 18th century onward, notably influenced by Mary Wollstonecraft. The growth of this theory in 1960s and 1970s focused on social and cultural inequalities in addition to political rights.

Issued highlighted in this study clearly shows that patriarchy, gender roles, discrimination and inequality with various branches including liberal, radical, postcolonial, and black feminism. As clearly outlined by this theory, the perspective focused primarily on women's experiences, and potentially neglecting men's viewpoints. The inequalities and cultural differences where women still face significant restrictions

which can alienate men and some women who might otherwise support gender equality, creating polarization rather than dialogue. According to Otto (2022) the principles of non-discrimination is often not respected, frequently in the area of women's right.

The study's critiques within feminisms, challenges each other's assumptions and approaches, sometimes resulting in disagreement over priorities and methodology, that the focus on critique itself can become counterproductive or self-limiting, with calls for feminism to move beyond constant criticism or existing systems towards new positive frameworks.

In furtherance, the feminist theorist highlights how the marginalization of women in the society contributes to their psychological alienation and social disempowerment. According to Kwork Pui-lan (2025) "feminist theology must take seriously the lived experienced of women, particularly those from post-colonial and minority contest, to unmask the layers forms of discrimination of theological language, liturgy, and to reflect equality and inclusiveness. The principles of equality and non-discrimination forms the basis of all human rights instruments and cut across all the rights found within human rights treaties influenced both the interpretation and of rights (Vandenhole, 2005).

Understanding the effect of discrimination against the female gender requires examining how power, social roles, identity, and learning interest within social institutions. By the application of the feminist theory, it can be deduced that deeper understanding of how discrimination is sustained and how it can be dismantled. Such analysis is essential for advocating for justice, equity and full inclusion within the society. This dual marginalization has had many women to seek alternative space when their leadership is affirmed. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) asserted that "fighting poverty requires direct policy interventions. Considering the fact that African countries are less effective in reaching their poor citizens". The theory of feminism faces criticisms about inclusivity, focus, representation, and strategic approach. The intersection of gender, race, class, and colonialism, upholds communalism and the centrality of the family. Unlike mainstream feminism that often centers on individual

liberation, African women emphasize harmony between men and women communal survival, and cultural relevance.

Summary and Conclusion

The female gender integrates spiritual, material, and communal values, which are deeply embedded in African societies, offering a culturally sensitives framework for social welfare and change. The study emphasize that women provide a valuable epistemological tool for gender studies, postcolonial theory, and cultural studies. It is acknowledged that the intersectional identities of African women shaped by globalization, race, colonialism, socio-economic class, argues that gender discrimination must be addressed across Africa. As a result, women are given lower responsibilities compared to men. Discrimination against the female folks has historically reinforced broader societal gender inequalities by legitimizing male authority in both cultural and traditional spheres. The studies shows that women with strong political or cultural values are less likely to hold leadership positions especially in corporate leadership and traditional roles, as they encounter gender barriers. These challenges have made it difficult for reforms to take place, even in denominations that claim to support gender justice.

In addition to analyzing the characteristics of gender inequality in Africa, this paper empirically studied the key drivers of gender equality in our society as it affects the well-being of people generally. It also draws out important policy implications for African countries. The model is estimated by Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method with country fixed effects. Therefore, a deeper understanding of the key determinants of gender equality in Africa is crucial for implementing effective policies to make Africa society more inclusive for economic and social development so as to reap its benefits. The study also revealed that inequality exacerbate social tension, violence against women and increased vulnerability.

Recommendations

- a. Women's participation in decision-making processes should be increased and promoted;
- b. Women's leadership in communities, organizations, and economic activities to ensure their voices are heard and their needs addressed;
- c. Need for skill development particularly in rural areas and informal sectors;
- d. Policy reforms should be advocated to dismantle patriarchy in Africa;
- e. There should be social and cultural change through campaign awareness and education programmes to shift social norms and foster equality in communities.

References

- African Customary and Religious Law Review 1 (2020). Anna-Sophia, B. (2022). *A critical introduction to Western Feminism – Liberation or Domination?* Seminar: Postcolonial theory and short fiction MAS-Eng-3. Wintersemester 20/21.
- Benda, F. (2008). *Project on a mechanism to address laws that discriminate against women*. Commissioned by: Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights-Women's Right ad Gender Unit. Pg. 1.
- Enakireru, E. O., & Edewor T. O. (2024). Appraisal of the Right of Women to Inheritance in African Society under Customary Law. *Journal of Policy & Governance*. Published by The Grassroots Institute, Canada
- Enweonwu, O. A., Hyginus, I. U., Ugomma, A. E., & Uchenna, N. O. (2023). Religion as the Matrix of Nigerian Culture. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)* Volume 5, Issue 2 Feb. 2023, pp: 304-309 www.ijaem.net.
- Godelier, M. (1981). The origins of male domination. *New Left Review*. <https://newleftreview.org/issues/i127/articles/maurice-godelier-the-origins-of-male-domination.pdf>
- Johnson-Bashua, A. O. (2020). African Traditional Religion, Gender Equality and Feminism. *South-South Journal of Humanities and international Studies*. Vol.3 No.2.
- Karami, R. A. (2021). The Relationship between Religion and Culture with an Emphasis on Jurisdictional Effects. *Journal of American Science (J Am Sci.)*; 17(11):20-29.
- Makama, G. A. (2013). Patriarchy and gender inequality in Nigeria: The way forward. *European Scientific Journal*. Vol 9 (17).
- Mofoluwawo, E. O. (2014). Social cultural and economic discrimination to women

- participation in Africa politics: The case of Nigeria. *International Journal of Learning & Development*. Macrothink Institute. Vol 4 (1).
- Oaikhena, I. M. (2021). *Policy pathways towards poverty reduction in the midst of Covid-19 pandemic in Africa: The case of Nigeria and Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC)*. Pandemic in the 21st Century: Multidimensional Approaches 2nd College of Management and Social Sciences 2021 Conference. Vol. 1 212-222.
- Oaikhena, I. M. (2022). *Morality practices among bureaucrats: a catalyst for peace and nation building*. *Department of Peace Studies and Conflict Resolution*. Faculty of Social Sciences, National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). Chapter 9. 153-169.
- Oaikhena, I. M. (2024). Community vigilante groups in Nigeria: a review of its activities and regulatory policies. *CERDEL Multidisciplinary Journal of African Development*. Vol. 2, 1-21.
- Oaikhena, I. M., & Aligbe, A. B. (2023). Rethinking redistributive policies for regulatory compliance in a democratic developing society. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management*. 9(2), 59-66.
- Oaikhena, I. M., & Osawe, C. (2012). Building strong democratic institutions: a panacea to good governance and policy implementation in Nigeria. *Kogi Journal of Politics. Anyingba, Nigeria*. Vol. 2 (2).
- Oaikhena, I. M., Agara, T., & Idehen, R. (2013). Behavioural dissonance in the change agents' effort of the re-entrants: implication for transfer of knowledge. *Benin Journal of Social Science*. 21 (1).
- Otto, D. (2022). Gender comment: why does the UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights Need a General Comment on Women? 14 (2002) *Canadian Journal of Women's Law 1*.
- Salisu, U., Oaikhena, I. M., Anas, A., Akongbowa, B. A. (2024). Exploring the relationship between politics and administration: Understanding the dichotomy. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Kuwait Chapter)*. 13 (2). 19-24.
- Udofia, C. (2021). African traditional values. Bolly. *Journal of Social Sciences*. 4 (1).
- Vandenhole, W. (2005). *Non-discrimination and equality in the view of the UN Human Rights Treaty*. *Bodies (Antwerp, Intersentia, 2005)*. CESCR general comment 16 on equal rights of men and women in the enjoyment of economic, social and cultural rights, E/C 12/2005/4, 11, page 2,3,10 and 22.